

HYGROTHERMAL EFFECTS ON FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF NATURAL FIBERS COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this work is to determine the influence of hygrothermal ageing on the mechanical proprieties and fatigue proprieties of natural fiber composite specifically of quasi-isotropic flax/epoxy composite. The result of quasi-static tensile test shows the degradation of proprieties of this material. Fatigue test were performed at 70% and 80% of ultimate tensile stress. The results show a great dissipation energy for ageing samples in the beginning of the fatigue cycle compared with unaged sample. Acoustic emission were used to follow the evolution of damage in this material and to characterize the mechanism damage in fatigue mode. Most damage of ageing sample was shown during the fatigue test compared with unaged and fiber pull-out damage mechanism was grown with ageing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Natural fiber composites (NFCs) are eco-friendly materials with good mechanical properties, low density, and good thermal insulation [1-2]. They compete with synthetic materials in several fields of application. However, the mechanical proprieties of NFC are susceptible to weathering effects which can greatly affect their durability. In structural applications, environmental factors such as temperature, humidity and ultraviolet (UV) rays can directly affect the mechanical properties. These materials should be carefully evaluated before being put into service. In this regard, several researchers have successfully shown that exposure to UV radiation and / or moisture causes degradation of mechanical properties and damage to the surface structure. This degradation is mainly due to different mechanism such as photo-radiation, thermal degradation, photo-oxidation, hydrolysis and swelling processes in the matrix as well as in the fibers themselves (lignin, cellulose, pectin and hemicellulose). The effect of moisture and temperature play a critical role in the service life because of hydrophilic and poor thermal resistance of natural fibers. In recent years, many studies on NFCs focussed on the improvement of the interface adhesion between fiber/matrix to increase their mechanical proprieties. Despite this growing interest, few studies have been conducted on the long-term durability behavior, particularly the combined effect of fatigue and aging. This lack of interest is due to the complexity of the damage mechanism in these materials and the complex evolution of various microscopic failure mechanisms especially under cyclic (fatigue) loading [1-3]. In addition to the multidirectional complex damage, the wide variability of results obtained with fatigue testing make it difficult to design reliable models for prediction and analysis of the fatigue behavior [4-7]. The potentially wide range of application of NFCs in engineering design make it necessary to

study the effect of the environment on the fatigue behavior. The purpose of this study is to determine the influence of the combined thermal and moisture effects on NFCs subject to fatigue through the use of hygrothermal testing. Unidirectional flax-epoxy NFC samples were manufactured by a thermo hydraulic press. Fatigue behavior of the samples was investigated to evaluate the effect of aging on their mechanical properties. Non-destructive technique such as acoustic emission (AE) were coupled with fatigue testing to identify damage evolution, to evaluate the correlation between the physical parameters of sound waves that occurred during the fatigue and the tensile tests [8], and to examine how hygrothermal ageing can possibly affect the different failure mechanisms.

2. EXPERIMENTATION

2.1. Composite fabrication

In order to evaluate the elastic properties of the material under study, plates of 30 cm x 25 cm were molded. Unidirectional flax-epoxy prepregs from LINEO NV «FlaxTape 100» were used for manufacturing the plates. Manual cutting and stacking of uncured prepregs was done by laying-up a configuration of $[0_2/90_2/\pm 45]_s$ to have a quasi-isotropic laminates with four different orientation of fibers (named FEH). A total of twelve plies were used in each sample. The plates were molded using thermo hydraulic compression molding technique at pressures of 15 bars. The temperature of the cure during the plates manufacturing was 165°C for 45 min. Specimen were cut out from the plates with a diamond blade cooled by water to avoid burning of the fibers. Each sample was dried during 24 h in the oven at 70°C to remove the moisture. The geometric dimensions of the specimens meet the standards ASTM D3039 for tensile tests (rectangular tensile test specimens of 25 mm × 250 mm). The characteristics of the prepreg and the composites plates are summarized in Table 1.

Type:	Fiber weight fraction	50%
FLAXTAPE © 110 Prepeg	Weight of flax M_s (g/m ²)	110 g de fiber/m ²
Theoretical density ρ_c (g/cm ³)	1.31	
Type: $[0_2/90_2/\pm 45]_s$	Fiber volume fraction	68%
	Void volume fraction	3.2%
Experimental density ρ_c (g/cm ³)	1.21±0.3	

Table 1: Characteristics of «FlaxTape © 110» and the plate

2.2. Hygrothermal ageing test

After the drying, batches of fifteen $[0_2/90_2/\pm 45]_s$ flax/epoxy specimens were submerged in distilled water and heated at 60 °C for the hydrothermal ageing. The evolution of degradation in the sample is obtained by a gravimetric analysis. The samples were periodically taken out of the batch and the weight of each sample was evaluated using an electronic precision balance every 48 hours. Weight change M_t for each specimen at the time t is calculated from a ratio of its initial weight W_0 to its weight at the time t, say $W(t)$, as follows:

$$M_t (\%) = \frac{W(t) - W_0}{W_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The diffusion coefficient was calculated using the following equation

$$D = \frac{\pi}{(4M_m)^2} \left(\frac{M_t h}{\sqrt{t}} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

Where M_m is a maximum moisture uptake at saturation at time t , h the thickness of the sample.

2.3. Mechanical tests

Tensile testing

Before studying the behavior of the material under fatigue loading, tensile tests were conducted to determine some basic material properties of non-degraded and degraded samples: Young's modulus, ultimate strength and failure strain. The tensile tests were performed for 5 unaged and aged specimens using an Instron model LM-U150 electromechanical testing machine, equipped with a 150 kN load cell and connected to a 50mm extensometer to register the strain during the test. The test were performed with a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min in accordance with ASTM D3039. The ultimate tensile strength and, the ultimate strain were recorded and the young modulus were determined in accordance with ASTM D3039.

Fatigue Test

Fatigue experiments (Figure 1) were performed in accordance with ASTM D3479 at room temperature to evaluate the durability of the material before and after aging. For 5 Hz fatigue experiments in air, the specimens were loaded on a hydraulic machine at $R = 0.1$. A load control mode was used. During fatigue testing, an extensometer, which was connected with the data acquisition system of the hydraulic machine, was fixed on the gage-length section of the specimen. Fatigue tests for unaged and aged specimen were carried at levels corresponding to the 70% and 80% of the ultimate tensile stress. The tests were performed on a MTS Model 647.10 servo-hydraulic testing machine, equipped with a 100 kN load cell. During fatigue testing, an extensometer was connected to the data acquisition system of the hydraulic machine, and fixed on the gauge-length section of the specimen to record the strain evolution. The continuous acquisition of the stress ($\sigma_{\min} \leq F/S \leq \sigma_{\max}$) by the load sensor and of the strain ($\epsilon_{\min} \leq \epsilon_x = \Delta L_x/L_0 \leq \epsilon_{\max}$) by the extensometer allows calculating Young's modulus for each cycle.

Figure 1: FEH sample submitted to fatigue testing coupled with an extensometer and acoustic apparatus

Acoustic emission

The analysis of specific damage phenomena occurring in the NFCs is done using Mistras PCI-2 acoustic emission (EA) data acquisition system. The AE measurements were achieved using two piezoelectric sensors placed on one side of the specimens with silicon grease attached on each adherent to secure the transducers specimen's surface. The frequency range of the sensor was 500 kHz to 1 MHz. An acoustic threshold level set at 35 dB was used to filter background noise. The signals from the piezo-electric transducers were amplified by 40 dB using a pre-amplifier and were displayed in real time on a computer screen with the AEWin™ software during the fatigue tests, on both the unaged and aged samples. Both fatigue and tensile tests were connected to the AE system for acquiring the amplitude and duration signal of the AE from both unaged and aged samples.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Water absorption

The figure 2 shows the evolution water absorption at 60°C for five specimens as a function of the square root of immersion time divided by thickness. The results reveal the fast swelling of the samples and the high moisture uptake behaviour in the beginning of water absorption time, followed by the saturation. In these experimental conditions the moisture saturation time is greatly shortened. This mainly due to the immersion of specimens in water and the high temperature of immersion. The moisture absorption and swelling affects the degradation of components of the matrix and the fibers in the material. This was observed by the little decrease of moisture uptake at saturation level and the yellowing of the water. The same trend was observed for other measurements and therefore there is good repeatability of this result.

Figure 2 Evolution of water absorption of [0/90/±45]_s flax/epoxy samples aged at 60°C

Diffusion coefficient and saturation weight gain are summarised in Table 2.

Sample	$D * 10^{-6}$ (mm ² /s)	M_m (%)
FEH aged	3.98±0.12	28.34±0.56

Table 2 Value of uptake weight saturation and diffusion coefficient of FEH aged samples

3.2. Mechanical proprieties

Static tensile testing

The influence of temperature and humidity on mechanical behaviour was assessed by testing unaged composites left in water at 60 °C for 12 days. These tests were done after drying the specimens in the oven at 70 °C during 24h. Figure 2 represents the typical stress-strain curves obtained. Two zones are observed. The first zone is linear and represents the elastic behaviour of composite. The modulus in Table 3 is calculated in this linear portion for both unaged and aged specimen. In this first zone the main difference between the unaged (Figure 3.b) and aged (Figure 3.a) stress-strain curves is the marked decrease of the slope after the ageing of the composites. The second zone becomes non-linear and represents the plastic behaviour of the composite. In this second zone the decrease of slope is moderate, and ultimate strains of 1% and 1,2% are obtained for unaged and aged composite, respectively. Table 3 resumes the mechanical proprieties of five aged and unaged samples.

Figure 3 Stress-strain curves of (a) aged and (b) unaged samples

Sample	σ_r (Mpa)	ϵ_r (%)	E (GPa)
FEH aged	145.16±9.19	1.20±0.08	15.76±0,90
FEH unaged	145±7.21	0.98±0.04	17.85±0.62

Tableau 3: Mechanical proprieties of aged and unaged samples

Fatigue testing

The evolution of the fatigue damage in the specimen was identified by the hysteresis curves at different number of cycles. Figures 4 shows the stress-strain hysteresis loops of early ($n/N_f=0$) and end ($n/N_f=1$) cycles during loading at two levels (70% and 80% ultimate tensile stress respectively) for both aged and unaged samples. Loops moving towards higher strains at each cycle were observed. This increasing of the strain is related to the cyclic creep effect [9]. The area enclosed within a loop, corresponds to the energy. At constant loading it decreases over time. It also increases with the loading because the different loop sizes. Higher dissipated energy of was observed for aged sample at the beginning of the cycle. The slope of the linear region in the stress-strain curve at each cycle was used to calculate the corresponding fatigue modulus (E_f).

Figure 4 Stress-Strain hysteresis loops of (a) aged and (b) unaged samples

The evolution of fatigue modulus that represents the ratio of maximum stress to maximum strain of hysteresis loops was plotted as function of normalized number of cycles to failure (Figure 5).

For all samples, the fatigue modulus decreases with the life ratio and depend on the loading level. The observed profiles present three stages of evolution:

- A zone with significant initial slope at the beginning of the curves.
- A constant slope zone
- A zone where the slope gradually increases again just before failure.

Similar result were observed by many authors [10-11]. It is concluded that the evolution of fatigue modulus for unaged and aged composite is similar.

Figure 5 Evolution of fatigue modulus as function of normalized fatigue life time of aged and unaged FEH samples

Acoustic Emission

Acoustic emission experiments were performed to compare the evolution of damage mechanisms between unaged and aged samples. Figure 6 shows a histogram of the number of hits as a function of the amplitude for aged and unaged samples obtained from fatigue tests carried at 70% and 80% ultimate tensile stress level. It can be observed that the number of hits occurs at around 38-40 dB. This amplitude range is characteristic of matrix damage in the composite material [12-14]. The range around 40-65 dB is characteristic of fibre pull-out [14-15]. In this range, the unaged material also presents less damage mechanisms than its aged counterpart. This indicates that ageing degraded the cohesion between matrix and fibres. Fiber pull-out is also more present for fatigue tests at 80% level of ultimate tensile [15].

Cumulative absolute energy acquired during AE tests is represented in Figure 7. Higher activity levels for aged samples are observed throughout the whole duration of the fatigue tests. This means that damage level was significantly higher. From Figure 7 it can be observed that absolute energy seems to evolve in stages, as was already observed from fatigue test data (Figure 5). Clearly the damage evolution is different for both aged and unaged samples. For aged samples the apparition of a new mechanism during the fatigue test explains the grow-up of cumulative energy during the fatigue test. Figure 8 clearly shows the presence of new damage mechanisms for aged sample. This also demonstrates the capacity of AE to distinguish damage mechanisms better during fatigue tests.

Figure 6 Comparison of distribution of AE signals during fatigue tests on flax/epoxy at 70% (a) and 80% (b) from ultimate tensile stress.

Figure 7 Cumulative AE energy vs time for unaged (a) and aged (b) flax/epoxy sample at 80% from ultimate tensile stress level

Figure 8 Picture of FEH aged and unaged flax/epoxy samples submitted of fatigue test

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper discussed experimental results on damage mechanisms of NFCs under fatigue loading and aging. The investigations show that hygrothermal ageing has a dominant degrading effect on the fatigue behaviour of flax-epoxy composites. The tensile tests showed that water ageing degrades considerably the Young modulus and increases the maximum strain of flax-fibre. The evolution of modulus during fatigue shows a similar behaviour of aged and unaged sample and demonstrates the incapacity to explain the damage in the samples.

Results also demonstrate the potential of AE as a tool to understand the damage mechanisms that occur during a fatigue test, and to evaluate the effect of weathering on the mechanical properties of this material.

As different tests continue to be performed, more fatigue and AE data will be added to our database to investigate the effect of moisture and weathering (combination of moisture, UV and thermal) on the fatigue life of NFCs at different level. Visual inspection of the test specimens will be done to confirm the different damage mechanism acquired from AE test. Extensions of this work include the study of the influence and sensitivity of each parameter of weathering on fatigue behaviour (UV rays, water absorption and temperature). Another avenue concerns the use of

multivariable analyses (such as thermography analysis coupled with the AE signals) to distinguish, the different damage mechanisms in more details.

5. REFERENCES

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